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Leveraging Artificial Intelligence to Enhance Oral Communicative Skills in French Language Education

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Abstract

As part of the current study, artificial intelligence (AI), specifically the "spoken conversation" function, will be examined in relation to teaching French as a foreign language, emphasizing oral reception, production, interaction and mediation. The authors examine the use of artificial intelligence (AI) to improve oral communicative language skills by creating individualized and interactive learning environments based on the Common Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). Through real-time speaking, learners can improve their pronunciation, rhythm, and accuracy as well as gain knowledge of various language structures and phonetic patterns. When artificial intelligence and spoken conversation are integrated into language learning in a manner that meets the needs and proficiency levels of students, their oral skills are enhanced.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Spoken Conversation, French Language Teaching, Foreign Language, Communicative Language Competences

1. Introduction

Several aspects of life, including education, have been profoundly affected by rapid technological advances. As a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, which forced educational institutions worldwide to close for an extended period of time (Krystalli, Mavropoulou, & Arvanitis, 2021), distance education, particularly vocational training, has seen significant growth. The shift towards e-learning has highlighted the importance of effective digital tools for maintaining educational continuity and supporting language learning. It has been shown that artificial intelligence (AI) is one of the most innovative technologies in the field of education, particularly when it comes to language learning (Mavropoulou & Arvanitis, 2023; Mavropoulou, 2023). By providing learners with personalized, interactive learning opportunities, artificial intelligence can greatly enhance their language skills (Mavropoulou & Arvanitis, 2023). As a result of AI applications, including chatbots and spoken conversation platforms (Mavropoulou & Arvanitis, 2023; Jeon, 2024), improve students' oral skills, students become more engaged, and

more autonomous (Mavropoulou & Arvanitis, 2023). As well as providing immediate feedback, interactive and personalized instruction, artificial intelligence facilitates learning in an effective manner. As a result of its advanced capabilities, artificial intelligence enables the creation of rich and diverse learning environments in which students can practice their language skills in real or simulated communication situations (Zou et al., 2023). Additionally, these technologies provide support for autonomous learning in addition to enhancing motivation and self-regulation.

Chatbots can be customised to meet the different needs of students by teachers (who play an important role in the learning process). It is important for teachers to adopt chatbots as aids and not as replacements for traditional teaching methods in order to achieve effective learning. Chatbots allow learners to take control of their language acquisition. The use of a chatbot with artificial intelligence combined with human experience is an attractive, autonomous and effective way of learning foreign languages. To date, these tools remain useful and are constantly being improved (Haristiani et al., 2019).

Chatbots are not intended to replace professionals in language learning. Compared to the more sophisticated artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms available today, linguistic experts have knowledge and experience. To be effective and efficient, technology-assisted language learning requires humans and chatbots to work in synergy, and this is a significant research challenge (Hwang & Chang, 2023).

There is a lot of research on chatbots in language education, which proves that the demand in this area is greater and more immediate. According to the study, the field of research on educational chatbots is still in its infancy and is expected to grow rapidly in the future. (Mavropoulou & Arvanitis, 2023).

2. Theoretical Framework

2.1. Overview of Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence refers to the development of computer systems that can perform tasks that traditionally require human intelligence, such as learning, problem-solving and decision-making (Russell & Norvig, 2020). Among the subfields of artificial intelligence are computer vision, robotics, machine learning, and natural language processing.

2.2. Subsectors of Artificial Intelligence

Some subsectors of Artificial Intelligence are: Machine learning, Natural processing systems, Robotic systems and Computer vision. A fundamental component of artificial intelligence is the development of algorithms and models capable of learning from data and making predictions and decisions without explicit programming instructions (Goodfellow, Bengio, & Courville, 2016). In machine learning, there are three types: supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning. Natural language processing systems can and do interpret, understand, and produce human speech as a technology (Jurafsky & Martin, 2023). A robotic system that uses artificial intelligence in conjunction with an operating system can and will perform tasks in the real world by sensing its surroundings and making real-time decisions (Siciliano & Khatib, 2016). Computer vision allows us to interpret and analyse images and videos gathered from the environment. Facial recognition and image analysis applications rely heavily on this technology (Szeliski, 2021).

2.3. Applications of Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence is a valuable tool that can enhance numerous aspects of our lives, including healthcare, education, autonomous vehicles, financial analysis, and customer service (Mavropoulou et al., 2023). Artificial intelligence is the future of language learning. It improves efficiency and effectiveness by developing personalized training programmes that provide immediate feedback to learners (Woolf, 2010). To get the most out of artificial intelligence and to exploit its benefits in education, what is needed is to grasp its core principles and potential.

2.3.1. Spoken conversation

This technology is also known as spoken dialogue or spoken interaction. It uses artificial intelligence to enable users to communicate naturally with computers. The system uses both natural language processing and voice recognition software to understand and respond to user commands.

2.3.2. Voice recognition

This technology is the process by which a computer system recognises the words spoken by a speaker. It uses artificial intelligence to enable users to converse naturally with computers. Voice recognition technology use advanced machine learning algorithms and neural networks to improve the accuracy and speed of recognition (Hinton et al., 2012). During the understanding and response to user commands, the system utilizes both natural language processing and voice recognition software.

2.3.3. Natural Language Processing (NLP)

Natural language processing (NLP) as a field of artificial intelligence, involves computer interaction with human languages. NLP systems analyse, understand, and produce human language in ways that are natural to users (Jurafsky & Martin, 2019). These technologies are used to process and understand users' spoken commands and produce appropriate and understandable responses.

2.3.4. Applications in Language Teaching

In foreign language teaching, spoken conversation can be used to practice not only the pronunciation, but it enhance oral reception, oral production and oral interaction communicative language activities. At this point, artificial intelligence comes to answer previous research gaps by researchers working on portable learning and language learning/teaching.

In a study that focused on the use and effectiveness of MALL in second and foreign language (L2) education and the potential of mobile devices as effective tools for providing language learning materials to students in terms of acquired language knowledge and skills, it showed that there is a huge potential in the field of MALL applications, but there is also inconsistency with the standards proposed by the Common European Framework, and that there is a greater need for empirical research in order to understand the potential of mall in foreign language learning.

In a more recent comparative study about Duolingo and Babbel, Arvanitis (2019, p. 21), points out that although learners found the language learning process very interesting and enjoyable, and consider the enjoyable features of the applications (quality of sound, graphics, audio and written rewards) to be factors of learning motivation, looking further at the communicative language skills and activities developed specifically by the Duolingo and Babbel platforms under the CEFR, we observe that they do not develop oral and written mediation, nor oral and written interaction, activities that are difficult to implement in digital environments". It also highlights the fact that "stand-alone online language learning platforms and digital applications with their pleasant nature seem to be suitable for use at low levels of language proficiency and can function as complementary and combinatorial tools in a foreign language teaching/learning process" (Arvanitis, 2019).

In a recent study (Mavropoulou & Arvanitis, 2023) researchers concluded that it is proven that chatbots can improve language learning. Through personalized, interactive and accessible language practice, learners can improve their proficiency and motivation. In order for chatbots to be effective, several factors such as their design, their integration into the curriculum and teachers' attitudes toward them need to be taken into account. The researchers pointed out that it is possible to adapt chatbots to meet the different needs of students from teachers, who play an important role in facilitating learning. It is important for teachers to adopt chatbots as aids and not as replacements for traditional teaching methods in order to achieve a harmonious and effective learning environment (Mavropoulou & Arvanitis, 2023).

Integrating spoken conversation bots into MALL applications or using them independently can significantly improve learners' language skills. It comes to complement stand-alone foreign language learning applications, as the development of spoken language production is something that is missing in conjunction with the CEFR specifications. The possibility of automated recording of the conversation that will be achieved is another strong stone that comes to contribute to foreign language learning and teaching as well.

2.3.5. Examples of Voice Conversation Technologies

Examples of spoken conversation technologies include digital assistants. Amazon Alexa which is Amazon's voice artificial intelligence that resides in the cloud, assists users from anywhere there is internet access and a device that can connect to it. Alexa can play a song, read the latest headlines, dim the lights in the living room and more. Google Assistant which is a voice of artificial intelligence available on many devices like Google Home and Google Pixel can do things like answer questions, play games, remind upcoming events, manage a calendar and more. Apple Siri, is designed to work on Apple's system, which includes iOS, WatchOS, macOS and TvOS devices. This OS integration allows users to use Siri with a similar experience across different devices. Google Assistant and Apple Siri use voice recognition and NLP technologies to interact with users (Hoy, 2018). In language teaching, platforms such as Duolingo and Rosetta Stone have incorporated spoken conversation features to provide students with real-time practice and feedback opportunities.

2.3.6. The European Common Frame of Reference for Languages (CEFR)

The European Common Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) is an important tool for language teaching and learning, providing a common system for assessing and describing language competences. The Council of Europe is establishing this organisation to guarantee transparency and consistency in language education across Europe.

The CEFR definitively sets out language proficiency levels, ranging from A1 (Beginner) to C2 (Proficient). The CEFR is made up of language activities, language skills and proficiency levels. Learners at each level of the Council of Europe (Council of Europe, 2022; Council of Europe, 2001) must demonstrate the skills that define their ability to use language effectively in a range of communicative contexts.

The CEFR is the definitive guide for developing and assessing French language curricula. Furthermore, CEFR standardization guarantees seamless collaboration and mobility of learners across Europe. The CEFR allows teachers to set clear learning objectives and adapt their teaching methods to suit their students' language proficiency levels (Little, 2006).

Oral communication is a crucial element of KEPIA. The CEFR levels provide a comprehensive description of oral production and comprehension skills, and they make it clear that learners must be able to interact effectively in a variety of language contexts (Council of Europe, 2022). Students will improve their skills in an interactive and personalized learning environment by using spoken conversation tools with the help of artificial intelligence.

The European Common Framework of Reference for Languages provides clear, definitive guidelines and standards for evaluating and developing language skills. The implementation of the KEPIA must be made more effective by incorporating artificial intelligence and voice communication into the educational process, which will enhance learners' oral skills.

3. Methods and Materials

3.1. Research Methodology

This study will provide a comprehensive analysis of the existing literature regarding the use of artificial intelligence for oral skills in French language instruction. It will employ a rigorous literature-based approach to achieve this. This research has been conducted by collecting, analysing and synthesising previous studies, articles

and reports in a systematic manner. A literature review will establish how existing technologies impact the learning of French.

3.2. Spoken Conversation Tools and Platforms

The most effective platforms for language learning are Duolingo, Babbel and Rosetta Stone. Babbel is the best language-learning platform on the market, period. Von Ahn (2013) designed it to use artificial intelligence in order to deliver personalized lessons. It offers language courses using the latest interactive technology and voice recognition. Babbel has been proven to improve pronunciation and comprehension in numerous studies (Nushi & Eqbali, 2018; Bajorek, 2017). Rosetta Stone is a long-term language learning platform on the market. It also improves pronunciation and comprehension through voice recognition technology. Rosetta Stone is highly effective, as numerous studies have shown it (Faradilla & Daulay, 2023; Firdaus, 2019; Kirova, 2011).

3.3. Sample and Participants

This study is a bibliographic endeavour. The sample will therefore include academic articles, books and technical reports related to artificial intelligence as a language instruction tool. To identify studies examining the impact of spoken French conversation on learning, research and scientific journals were consulted. Using the findings of the selected sources, a data analysis compared and contrasted the findings.

4. Enhancement of pronunciation and rhythm in the production of spoken language

Artificial intelligence is an effective tool for improving students' pronunciation and rhythm when learning French. To communicate effectively in a foreign language, you must master pronunciation and rhythm through extensive practice and direct feedback (Thomson & Derwing, 2015; Derwing & Munro, 2015; Saito, 2012; Celce-Murcia, M., Brinton & Goodwin, 2010; Levis, 2005).

4.1. Artificial Intelligence and Pronunciation Correction

Artificial intelligence technologies, such as spoken conversation applications, are an effective tool for pronunciation practice in real-time, which improves learning. The platform's ability to identify and correct pronunciation errors help students improve their speech accuracy. Levis (2018) supports that real-time feedback is essential for developing correct pronunciation. Students can and should correct their mistakes immediately, learning from them as a result.

4.2. Rhythm and Vocal Skills

According to Derwing and Munro (2015), smooth speech flow and correct accent placement are essential for understanding spoken speech. The spoken conversation application is an indispensable tool for students. It enables them to identify and suggest improvements to rhythm anomalies.

4.3. Practical Examples

A study conducted by Neri, Mich, Gerosa, and Giuliani (2008) proves that using voice recognition technology significantly improves students' pronunciation and rate. This platform allows students to hear and repeat phrases, receive feedback, and adjust their speech accordingly.

The most effective way to enhance pronunciation and rhythm is to integrate artificial intelligence and spoken conversation into French language instruction. Students will undoubtedly improve their oral production and interaction skills and be able to communicate effectively in French. They will do this by receiving direct feedback and engaging in interactive practice.

4.4. Development of Language Structures and Vocabulary

Learn a foreign language by developing language structures and vocabulary is a very important aspect of learning a foreign language. The use of spoken conversation and artificial intelligence to achieve this is an innovative way in this era. The technology allows learners to interact with tailored educational programs that meet their specific needs and abilities. They also have access to a wide range of language models that help them learn the language.

4.5. Training in Pronunciation and Grammar

Advanced voice recognition algorithms enable Rosetta Stone and Duolingo to identify inconsistencies and errors in students' utterances in real time with precision.

4.6. Adapting to Students' Needs

Artificial intelligence allows us to customize educational materials based on the needs of individual students. By analysing usage data and student performance, platforms can and will adjust exercise difficulty and provide specific exercises that are tailored to strengthen specific language structures.

4.7. Vocabulary enhancement

Students must be able to repeat new words and phrases in order to learn new vocabulary. AI platforms facilitate this by presenting new words and phrases in various situations, making them easier to comprehend and retain. Furthermore, the interactive exercises and games ensure students actively utilize new vocabulary, which improves retention.

4.8. Real Communication Scenarios

Students must apply language structures and vocabulary in practical circumstances when learning them. They can apply their knowledge in practical situations by interacting with simulated conversations and creating realistic scenarios using artificial intelligence. Furthermore, this enhances comprehension and usage of natural spoken language, as well as vocabulary acquisition.

Artificial intelligence and spoken conversation are a powerful combination for teaching French. Continuous feedback, customized content and simulations of real-life communication situations are the most effective and efficient ways to help learners improve their language skills.

4.9. Examples and Results of Using Voice Conversation

It is clear from studies and applications that learning French through spoken conversation is an effective method. The following are a few examples and results.

4.9.1. Example 1: Duolingo

Using the popular language learning platform Duolingo, users can improve their oral communication skills through interactive exercises that provide immediate feedback on accuracy and rhythm as they practice. Using this platform regularly leads to significant improvements in the production of oral speech according to research (Vesselinov & Grego, 2012).

4.9.2. Example 2: Rosetta Stone

TruAccent™ allows students to compare their pronunciation with native speakers and receive immediate feedback. Rosetta Stone is another popular platform that utilizes voice technology to learn languages. Research conducted by Neri, Mich, Gerosa, and Giuliani (2008) proves the effectiveness of voice recognition technology in improving students' pronunciation.

4.9.3. Example 3: Google Assistant and Alexa

The use of digital assistants, such as Google Assistant and Alexa, for language learning, allows users to interact with each other and request translations, as well as practice their pronunciation. As studies have demonstrated, digital assistants can assist students in learning languages through personalized feedback and simulations of real-life conversational situations (Ji, Han & Ko, 2023; Hsu, Chen & Yu, 2023; Huang, Hew & Fryer, 2022).

4.10. Summary Results

There are a number of ways in which French language learners can benefit from voice conversation:

Improved supply: Students are able to speak more accurately and naturally (Neri et al., 2008).

Improved confidence: Students feel more comfortable and confident when speaking and when they receive direct feedback.

Repeated exposure to natural pronunciations and dialogues is the most effective way to enhance oral reception (Vesselinov & Grego, 2012).

AI technologies are being used to provide students with a more personalised learning experience (Kasneci et al., 2023, Klanja-Milievi & Ivanovi, 2021) that make it easier for students and teachers to adapt to the needs of their learning (Liu, Lomovtseva, & Korobeynikova, 2020).

5. Oral reception

5.1. Various spoken conversation standards

Artificial intelligence is an indispensable tool for learners of a foreign language. It allows them to be exposed to different phonetic patterns during spoken conversations, which improves their auditory perception and comprehension. Students must be exposed to a variety of phonetic patterns to understand accents and dialects in the target language (Vanderplank, 2010).

Artificial intelligence technologies such as voice recognition and voice synthesis allow students to listen to and interact with a variety of phonetic patterns. Repeated exposure to various voices and speech styles will undoubtedly improve the ability to understand spoken language (Graham, 2006).

Furthermore, AI-powered spoken conversation platforms provide the best learning experiences by adapting the difficulty and complexity of speech to the learner's level. Artificial intelligence can and should be used to provide feedback and strategies for improving listening comprehension by analysing student performance (Derwing & Munro, 2005).

Multimodal data (such as audio and text) can be used to gain a deeper understanding of auditory signals and develop effective auditory strategies. AI provides real-time feedback, which is essential for this process (Field, 2008).

5.2. Developing listening skills

Oral reception is essential for learning a foreign language in an educational setting. There is no question that communication and interaction are fundamental skills. Artificial intelligence technology, especially those which involve spoken conversation, is the most effective way to improve students' listening abilities.

AI is the most effective means of developing effective listening skills in language teaching. It provides students with the opportunity to be exposed to natural, authentic language input, which is essential for developing effective listening skills. Spoken conversation provides the ideal dynamic learning environment thanks to its interactive nature, which allows students to interact with voice models that simulate real-life conversations (Hsu, M. H., Chen & Yu, 2023; Ji, Han & Ko, 2023; Huang, Hew & Fryer, 2022).

Students must be exposed to a variety of phonetic patterns to identify and understand different accents and rhythms. Furthermore, students who practice listening skills with artificial intelligence platforms demonstrably improve their ability to follow fast and complex language patterns (Huang, Teo, & Zhou, 2019; Lebedeva et al., 2017). Spoken conversation technologies boost students' self-esteem and confidence by providing real-time feedback. Students are more likely to recognise and correct their mistakes if they receive immediate corrections and explanations (Tyrer, 2021; Malmberg, Järvelä & Kirschner, 2014). These technologies also lead to increased student engagement and enthusiasm. Incorporating spoken conversation into language teaching not only improves listening skills, but also promotes students' active participation and critical thinking (Richards & Rodgers, 2014; Huang, 2010; Nunan, 1999).

5.3. Case Studies and Data Analyses

This section presents case studies and data analyses focusing on the use of AI and spoken conversation to improve the production and comprehension of spoken language in French language teaching.

5.4. Case studies

5.4.1. ChatGPT case study

Particular interest presents the case of spoken conversation in the ai open application of ChatGPT. With the right instructions from the foreign language teacher, this service can be exploited. The student can give instructions in the application and participate in simulated conversations by practicing vocabulary, trying to pronounce correctly and also to understand the respective interlocutor (artificial intelligence). Then, as the conversation history is saved, the student can keep the transcript and work on it with the teacher or on his/her own, improving his/her skills. Also, he can discuss in any language, ask questions, translate. Here is an example of such a use.

Figure 1: Example of use 1

Figure 2: Example of use 2

Figure 3: Example of use 3

Figure 4: Example of use 4

Figure 5: Example of use 5

5.4.2. Case Study: Using the Duolingo Application to Improve Speech

The second case study examines the use of the Duolingo application, which incorporates artificial intelligence technologies for language learning. Research by Vesselinov and Grego (2012) showed that users of the app showed significant improvement in their language skills, particularly in pronunciation and listening comprehension, within a few months of using the app.

5.4.3. Case Study: applying Rosetta Stone and developing oral skills

The third case study examines the Rosetta Stone app, which uses AI technologies to facilitate language learning. Students using the app showed undeniable improvements in oral production and comprehension, particularly when used alongside traditional teaching methods (Nst, Daulay & Dewi, 2023).

5.5. *Comparative Analysis of Teaching Methods*

Studies proved that AI and traditional teaching methods are effective for teaching spoken language (González-Fernández, 2023; Lord, 2016). The results were definitive: students who used AI technologies, such as Duolingo and Rosetta Stone, demonstrated substantial gains in accuracy and fluency compared to those who adhered solely to traditional teaching methods.

6. **Spoken conversation vs Traditional Methods**

6.1. *Advantages and Disadvantages of AI*

Artificial intelligence has transformed French language teaching. There is no doubt that it offers advantages over traditional methods, although there are also disadvantages. In this section, we will present a clear and objective analysis of the main points of comparison, supported by real-world reports and studies.

6.2. *Benefits of Artificial Intelligence*

Personalized learning is the future. AI provides personalized lessons and tailored feedback, without a doubt ensuring each student receives the support they need to succeed. This technology allows for continuous assessment and real-time adaptation of learning content (Holmes, Bialik, & Fadel, 2019).

Students receive immediate feedback on their pronunciation, intonation, and language accuracy through spoken conversation, allowing them to correct errors immediately (Chen et al., 2021).

The best way to learn is through interaction. AI allows students to create interactive learning environments that encourage active participation and real-time practice with virtual peers (Marco-Fondevila et al., 2022).

Accessibility is guaranteed. AI platforms are accessible anytime and from anywhere, facilitating continuous practice and repetition (Johnson et al., 2019).

6.3. *Disadvantages of AI*

The lack of human contact is a problem. Despite advances in technology, it is an irrefutable fact that interaction with a machine cannot fully replace human contact and the authenticity of communication with a teacher or classmate (Beerends & Aydin, 2024). Technical problems will inevitably arise. Reliance on technology can and will lead to problems due to technical errors or incompatibilities that will interrupt or hinder the learning process (Smith & Anderson, 2017). Coping with complexity is essential. AI will undoubtedly face challenges in managing the complexities and nuances of human language, especially at advanced levels or in specific communication situations (Li et al., 2022). These are two more significant barriers to AI adoption. The cost of installing and maintaining AI systems is a significant barrier to access for all educational institutions (Brown & Adler, 2021).

6.4. *Effectiveness and Efficiency*

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and voice conversation in French language teaching is an effective and efficient method, as evidenced by multiple studies. The following reports definitively show the benefits of using AI in language education.

Pronunciation improvement is possible. L. (2019) states that the use of AI in pronunciation training will significantly improve the accuracy and clarity of students' pronunciation. Real-time vocal feedback allows students to immediately correct their mistakes, increasing the effectiveness of learning. Vocabulary and language structures are enhanced. Spoken conversation is an effective tool for developing a richer vocabulary and more complex language structures (Beck, McKeown & Kucan, 2013; Poveda, 2012). Students using AI platforms for language learning demonstrably improve their oral comprehension, as reported by Li et al. (2018). Spoken conversation provides exposure to different phonetic patterns, which enhances reception skills. Immediate feedback is key to helping students understand their errors and correct them in real time (Narciss, 2008; Shute, 2008; Hattie & Timperley, 2007). AI reduces the time required to learn new language skills. Learners who use spoken conversation for language learning complete learning programs more quickly compared to traditional methods (Sun, 2023; Zou, Reinders et al. 2023). AI tailors learning activities to the needs of each learner, allowing for a more personalised approach and increasing the efficiency of the learning process (Huang et al., 2020).

7. Study Conclusions

Artificial intelligence (AI) and spoken conversation are far superior to traditional teaching methods for learning the French language. Comparative studies have irrefutably shown that learners who use artificial intelligence speak their language with greater rhythm, pronunciation, and accuracy.

A number of studies have demonstrated that students who learn languages through artificial intelligence platforms perform better in oral speech production than those who learn languages using traditional methods (Shi, J., Sitthiworachart & Hong, 2024; Chang, Park, & Suh, 2024; Belda-Medina & Calvo-Ferrer, 2022; Wang & Han, 2022). The same students also showed clear signs of increased motivation and confidence during lessons. Furthermore, AI provides students with more accurate and faster feedback than human feedback. It identifies and corrects errors immediately, thus improving oral reception and oral production (AbuEl-Reesh & Abu-Naser, 2018). Spoken conversations are the best way to learn French, where oral variations can be challenging. They improve oral reception skills by exposing students to different phonetic patterns and dialects (Byrd, Huang & Edwards, 2022).

Artificial intelligence provides students with the best learning opportunities. They are interactive and flexible, and can be tailored to each student's individual needs and pace. This is a clear advantage over traditional learning methods (El-Sabagh, 2021). The best way to improve students' oral skills and make the French language instruction process more attractive and effective is to integrate artificial intelligence.

8. Discussion

This study proves that artificial intelligence, particularly spoken conversation, markedly enhances oral language production and reception in French language classrooms. Students taught using spoken conversation tools demonstrably outperform those taught using traditional methods in terms of pronunciation, rhythm, and accuracy (Saran, Seferoglu & Cagiltay, 2009; Lord, 2008). It is evident from numerous studies that exposure to diverse phonetic patterns through artificial intelligence significantly enhances oral reception skills and oral production skills (Ji, Han & Ko, 2023; Goh & Vandergrift, 2021, Ifenthaler, Mah & Yau, 2019).

9. Conclusions

9.1. Main Findings

This study proves that AI is an invaluable tool for learning French, particularly through spoken conversation. Spoken conversation improve pronunciation and rhythm. This is because students receive immediate feedback and corrections (Xu et al., 2019). Furthermore, familiarising students with linguistic and phonetic patterns undoubtedly enhances their oral reception skills (Li & Hegelheimer, 2013). A number of studies have demonstrated that students make significant progress when using AI tools, which allow them to advance according to their individual needs and strengths (Hwang & Tu, 2021; Chen, Chen & Lin, 2020; Holmes, Bialik & Fadel, 2019).

9.2. Contribution of Artificial Intelligence in Language Education

Artificial intelligence will undoubtedly facilitate a number of innovative ways to learn languages. Spoken conversations are an effective way to learn. This approach allows students to practice their language in a direct, interactive manner without the need for constant teacher attention (Nunan, 2015). This results in learners remaining engaged for longer (Chun et al., 2016). To improve understanding and communication, you must practice oral language and reception constantly (Derwing & Munro, 2015).

9.3. Final Thoughts and Proposals

French language learning is most effective when combined with artificial intelligence and spoken conversation. New studies must be conducted in order to examine the long-term effects in greater detail and improve existing technologies. Moreover, further research should be conducted for analysing the impact of artificial intelligence on other language skills, such as reading and writing, in order to confirm the findings in various age range and educational environments. The development and evaluation of new technologies for oral communication are being carried out in order to integrate them into existing platforms. As part of the CEFR specifications, it does not include the development of spoken language production applications, which will complement stand-alone foreign language learning programs. The possibility of automated recording of the conversation that will be achieved is another strong stone that also comes to contribute to foreign language learning and teaching. Finally, it has the potential to redefine language education, offering tools that improve language learning and comprehension in ways that were unimaginable until recently.

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